

Factorization Structure of Composite Fermat Numbers Modulo 384
(10.5281/zenodo.17201213)

For Fermat numbers $F(n)=2^{(2)^n}+1$ with $n>4$, there exist integers $m,k>1$ such that

$$F(n) = (384m - 127)(384k + 1).$$

The identity is

$$(384m - 127)(384k + 1) = k(384^2 m - 48768) + 384m - 127.$$

This decomposition relies on the residue classes “ $384n+257$ ” and “ $384n+1$ ”. Since it does not appear as a separate theorem in the literature, it is briefly recorded here.25/09/2025

Ender UYGUN
Çanakkale/Türkiye